

Supplement to **Towards improved methodology to measure the uptake of mammography in populations using insurance claims: a case study from Delaware, USA**

Summary results for 2019 mammography data

- *Observed HCCD data presumed misclassified*
 - Total screening mammograms in Delaware: 40,971
 - Statewide averaged uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above: 177
 - Supplemental Figure 1: Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware.
 - Census tract minimum, maximum: 56, 392
- *Adjusted HCCD data for presumed misclassification*
 - Statewide averaged uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above, median and 95% simulation interval: 229 (95% simulation interval: 224, 233)
 - Difference compared to observed per 1,000 women aged 40 and above: 52 (95% simulation interval: 47, 56)
 - Supplemental Figure 1: Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware.
 - Census tract minimum, maximum: 56, 392
 - Supplemental Figure 2: Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware

- *Sensitivity of DHIN and Census specifications*
 - DHIN-specification: Median of 93% across all census tracts in the State
(range: 73%, 100%)
 - Census-specification: Median of 67% across all census tracts in the State
(range: 41%, 96%)
 - Correlation: 38%
 - Supplemental Figure 3: Histogram of sensitivities based on the DHIN-specification and Census-specification adjustment methods.
 - Supplemental Figure 4: Blant-Altman plot for agreement between the DHIN-specification and Census-specification adjustment methods.

Supplemental Figure 1. Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware. Mammography uptake was measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2019 and are presumed underreported.

Supplemental Figure 2. Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware. Mammography uptake was measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2019, adjusted for presumed underreporting, and depicts the medians of 10,000 Monte-Carlo simulations. See text for details.

Supplemental Figure 3. Histogram of sensitivities based on the DHIN-specification (γ) and Census-specification (η) adjustment methods. Values derived from 10,000 Monte-Carlo simulations adjusting observed mammography uptake measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2019. See text for details.

Supplemental Figure 4. Bland-Altman plot for agreement between the DHIN-specification and Census-specification adjustment methods. Each point represents a census tract in Delaware, the y-axis is the difference between the two specifications, and the x-axis is the average of the two specifications. The solid line represents the average difference in measurements between the two specifications, while the dashed lines represent the 95% confidence interval limits for the average difference. Monte-Carlo simulations adjusting observed mammography uptake measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2019. See text for details.

